

Inventory control of Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas towards organization development

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Abstract

This research examined inventory control management of Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas towards organization development. The source of data collection for this study was primary source of data. Data collected for the study, was analyzed using SPSS 16.0 statistical method to enable the research draw inferences if there is a significant relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables as stated in the study. The findings revealed that there is a significant difference between profitability and lead time, as well as between cost saving and stock-out. It was observed that inventory practices, policies, and control system enhance their profitability by constantly using its resources to generate revenues in excess for the organization, the organization should deliberately ensure that unnecessary cost are minimized to enable them to constantly increase their profile base. The organization should effectively and timely adopt Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) process, between the initiation and execution in placement of an order and delivery of products. The organization should consciously ensure that they do not run out of stock to avoid their inventory to be exhausted.

Keywords: Inventory control; management; organization development.

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Introduction

Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas initially started with manufacturing of all kinds of furniture for, both national and international use. Then, with the inclusion of some investors such as Gani Umoru and Mariam Imonikhe, the company was diversified into construction and building of roads and houses having; Alhaji Abubakar as the chairman and also the founder of the company. The company also went into transportation of different types of Limestone to all parts of Nigeria, with more than 60 trucks and other official cars for top management. They decided to veer into the oil and gas business in 2016 renaming the company from Abubakar Enterprise to Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas. The company is a locally controlled corporation with a worth of two billion Nigeria currencies. It also has three (3) branches with the head office in Edo State, Benin City, Nigeria and staff strength of four hundred and forty-four (444) workers.

Inventory control was not considered to be essential in the past. Nonetheless, modern businesses are beginning to use efficient inventory control. This is because inventory management is strategically important to an organization's growth and survival; if it is managed poorly, it will result in a loss of clients and a drop in sales. Careful inventory management guarantees that the resources are available when needed and minimizes depreciation, theft, and waste (Ogbadu, 2009). Moreover, it is a clear fact that the primary objective of most organizations is to maximize profits as well as identifying and serving the needs of potential customers. This profit motive, being the main source of expansion and continued existence of the organization, therefore, serves as the basis on which the development of the organization can be evaluated over time while all effort is geared towards cost minimization.

According to Juneja (n.d.), keeping a lean inventory and exercising control are essential components of good inventory management practices. Reconciling the stock balances and appropriately monitoring the inventory moving into and out of the stockroom are also included. Inventory control is crucial to the whole sale distribution industry and should be prioritized to ensure the success of the company. Having more control over one's goods is inventory control. You may reduce costs, expedite order fulfillment, and stop fraud by being aware of what you have, where it is kept in your warehouse, and when stock comes in and goes out. Inventory control systems can also be used to balance your accounts, determine your present assets, and provide financial reports.

Maintaining the proper balance of stock in the warehouse is made possible by taking total control of your inventory. Knowing how much inventory you have in your warehouse will help you avoid losing a sale that could have been avoided if you had known how much you needed to fill the order. Should your company continue to face inventory problems, such as backorders and missing orders, you could lose sales when they move to another company.

The primary benefits of having an efficient inventory control system are improved customer service and a more up-to-date understanding of the products that are and are not selling. Different organizations manage their inventories in different ways. You can maintain a record of returns and newly received inventory in addition to selecting to have a column where you deduct what you ship and sell. However, this is an extremely time-consuming and tedious process that may be frustrating because it is prone to human error. Errors can occur and tracking them down would require painstakingly determining who made the mistake, why, and where. This is when inventory automation comes in useful.

Essentially, the more efficient your inventory system is, the less paperwork you will have to do. Using a service provider can be far more convenient than doing the inventory procedure by hand. They can also allow you to integrate with any multichannel integration that you would like to use or with enterprise resource planning (ERP) solutions. Regardless of how many consumers are making purchases at once, an automated system also enables you to use gear such as barcode scanners and printers to keep everything under control and ensure that your inventory data is maintained in real time. Some are even made to track a product's whereabouts within a storage facility, which is very useful when it comes time to retrieve and package the item for distribution.

Increased efficiency: Employees can focus more on other important duties because they are not required to physically monitor the inventory, and there is also a reduction in the amount of paperwork.

Inventory mastery: You have access to all of your inventory and are aware of its location within the storage facility, which is especially useful if you operate several warehouses in various states. Additionally, it saves you from having to communicate with your staff members on a regular basis to obtain stock data updates.

Better customer experience: Customers can receive their orders considerably more quickly and accurately if you have excellent control over your stocks. Customers will receive their orders faster if you can quickly inform them of your stock levels and easily obtain data about whether you have the goods in stock or need to refill.

In essence, inventories are collections of resources kept on hand in anticipation of future sales or production. One could consider inventories to be an idle resource with a marketable value. Improved inventory control would free up funds for more productive uses of capital (Ghosh & Kumar, 2003). According to Cummings and Worley (2017), corporate growth is the process of improving administrative capabilities through methodical actions. It also cares about the method by which things are accomplished. The goal of corporate growth is to enable individuals to collaborate more successfully, enhance organizational procedures like strategy creation and execution, and ultimately support organizational change (Armstrong, 2010; Onikoyi et al., 2017).

Given this, inventory control and management are essential for any business to succeed and should receive specific attention. Thus, it suggests that the oil and gas company's strategic focus should be on efficient inventory control and management. Inventory control management is crucial since any savings on inventory costs will have a significant impact on lowering production costs, which will enhance the growth of the company. Because the organization wants to reach its goal, effective inventory control is sometimes necessary. Organizations must therefore make every effort to lower inventory costs in order to minimize the overall cost of manufacturing. Effective inventory control management ultimately impacts an organization's ability to survive and grow in a cutthroat commercial environment (Tempelmeier, 2006).

Since inventory is the lifeblood and central component of every organization's overall development, it is widely believed to be essential to its successful operation (Ballou, 2005 as cited by Kairu, 2015). In industrial enterprises, inventory frequently makes up as much as 30% of the entire capital spent. This was corroborated by Gavett (1968), who said that it might account for up to 90% of working capital and 33% of the organization's assets. In light of this, one may argue that it is necessary to examine the costs associated with sustaining particular inventory levels because a sizeable portion of cash is invested in them. There are expenses associated with both having too much and too little inventory. Additionally, a sizable sum of money is needed to allocate to them because businesses, both in rich and developing nations, maintain extensive inventory control (Amachree et al., 2017).

As expressed by Beer and Nohria (2000), organization development operates as: 'a system-wide process of data collection, diagnosis, action planning, intervention and evaluation.' It can also be applied to resolve issues that arise inside the company or to examine a procedure and identify a more productive way of carrying out tasks. An intentional plan, organizational-wide effort to improve an organization's effectiveness and/or help it accomplish its strategic objectives is known as organization development. It includes long-term training programs that are designed to bring about a systematic change in the views, opinions, and actions of employees. It is frequently described as action oriented. Usually, it begins with a thorough assessment of the needs and status quo across the entire organization. It is by its very nature interdisciplinary, utilizing methods from the behavioral sciences, mainly psychology and sociology (including learning, motivation, and personality theories). Clinical epidemiology, systems thinking, complexity thinking, capacity building, and organizational learning are some of the emerging linked topics. Real change is actually produced by the network of relationships and cooperation between persons and organizations functioning within their own social, political, cultural, and economic contexts—often referred to as "institutions"—as is becoming more widely acknowledged. This entails acknowledging that, in order for organizational development to be successful, efforts at both the upper and lower "personnel" levels of the organization must be included. In light of this, it would be reasonable to argue that the discipline of organization development comprises a continuous, methodical approach to bringing about meaningful organizational transformation.

Proper inventory control is regarded as a possible driver for increasing profit margins (Osei-Mensah, 2015). The best course of action is to determine the ideal amount of inventory that an organization should keep in order to minimize total inventory costs. Profitability and the company's reputation will both increase with an effective inventory management system. It will make it possible for the business to start projects on schedule and produce high-quality final goods. A company's efficiency is increased when it puts in place efficient inventory management systems. Having seen the various emphases on organization development and its interrelation to inventory control as postulated above, adopting effective inventory control and practices by Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas is necessary. It is in this light that the study will be conducted to address the inventory control and practice problems in many organizations in Nigeria particularly in Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas. The gap in this study therefore is that not much research work has been done on inventory control of oil and gas company in Nigeria. This therefore is a need for further research work in this regard, so as to find out if adequate inventory control and practices can help oil and gas guarantee organization development with reference to Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas.

Statement of the Problem

The study focused on the inventory control and management of Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas towards organization development. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the inventory control and management practices that are being used by Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas in terms of:
 - 1.1 Profitability
 - 1.2 Cost savings
 - 1.3 Lead time
 - 1.4 Stockout
2. What are the inventory policies and control system that are being used to ensure organization development?

Hypothesis

In this study, the researchers used a null hypothesis, which implies that there is no statistical significance between variables.

Ho: There is no significant difference on the inventory control system and practices and organization development.

Methodology

Research Design

In the course of this study, survey methodology was used to analyze the data gathered. The survey technique was chosen in place of alternative methods as a result of its originality. The survey instrument for this study was questionnaire administered personally to the sampled respondents in this study. The SPSS 16.0 statistical method was adopted in analyzing the data collected for the study.

Sampling Design

The data collated in this study will be managed using simple random sampling techniques. The purpose of using simple random sampling in this study is that it gives equal opportunity to every member selected in the study to be represented in the study.

In this study, a sample size of twenty (20) respondents was selected from eight departments of the Abumorako Oil and Gas namely: Administration Department, Purchase Department, Sales Department, Engineering Department, Works Department, Haulage Department, Maintenance Department and Transportation Department using simple random sampling techniques to get a sample size of twenty (20) respondents each from the eight elected departments making it a total of 160 respondents for the study.

The survey for this study was done through questionnaires. The questionnaire was structured into two sections with section 'A' comprising of bio-data information of respondents, and section 'B' containing questions with five Likert scale method; requiring the respondents to indicate the following: Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Strongly Disagree, and Disagree to the questions raised. One hundred and sixty (160) questionnaires were distributed, and out of which one hundred and forty seven (147) were retrieved and were used for the analysis.

Statistical Treatment

All data gathered in this study were analyzed using SPSS 16.0 statistical method to enable the research draw inferences if there is a significant relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables as stated earlier in the study using analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Discussion on How the Test of Hypotheses were Derived

The test of hypothesis in this study were derived by formulating a model for the study that enable the researcher to analyze the variables as shown below:

$$ORGDEV = f(PRFITAB/LDTM, CSTSAV/STKOUT, INVPRACNTRSYS)$$

$$ORGDEV = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1PRFITAB/LDTM + \alpha_2CSTSAV/STKOUT + \alpha_3INVPRACNTRSYS + \epsilon_0$$

Where: Organization Development (Dependent Variable)

Profitability and Lead Time, Cost Saving and Stock-Out, Inventory Practices and Control Systems

(Independent variables)

ORGDEV = Organization Development

PRFITAB/LDTM = Profitability and Lead Time

CSTSAV/STKOUT = Cost Saving and Stock-Out

INVPRACNTRSYS = Inventory Practices and Control Systems

ϵ_0 = Error term

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographic profile (N=147)

Profile	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	87	59
	Female	60	41
Age	Below 20	10	7
	21-30	20	14
	31-40	60	41
	41-50	27	18
	51 and above	30	20
Educational Attainment	Grade	60	41
	Senior High	12	8
	Bachelors	50	34
	Masters	10	7
	Doctorates	7	5
	Others	8	5
Years of Working	Below 3	40	27
	4-6	90	61
	6-8	7	5
	9 and above	10	7

Table 1 above illustrates that in terms of gender, 59% of the respondents are males, while 41% are females. From the above result, there were more male respondents than female respondents. In terms of age, it presents that 7% of the respondents were below 20 years old, 14% were between 21 to 30, 41% were between 31 to 40, 18% were 41 to 50, while 20% were 51 and above. This implies that the respondents are adults and are between the ages of 31 to 40 years.

In terms of educational attainment, 41% of the respondents have finished grade levels, 8% have senior high school, 34% have bachelors, 7% have masters, 5% have doctorates, while the other 5% have other educational attainments. Thus, this means that the respondents are educated. It is also displayed that in terms of years of working, 27% of the respondents indicated that they have work below three years, 61% said they have worked between four to six years, 5% said they have worked between six to eight years, while 7% indicate that they have worked nine and above years. This is an indication that majority of the respondents have worked between four to six years.

Table 2. Industry inventory practices and control systems to ensure profitability

Profitability	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Two-bin System	4.38	0.639	Agree
Budgetary Control System	4.45	0.651	Agree
Economic Order Quantity	4.53	0.718	Strongly Agree
Perpetual Inventory Control System	4.37	0.704	Agree
Order Cycling System	4.22	0.866	Agree
Grand Mean	4.39		Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Undecided; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

In the table shown above, the analysis indicates that two-bin system has a mean response of 4.38 and the standard deviation is 0.639. The standard deviation of 0.639, therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response. Budgetary control system has a mean response of 4.45 and a standard deviation of 0.651. The standard deviation of 0.651 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.45. Economic order quantity has a mean response of 4.53 and a standard deviation of 0.718. The standard deviation of 0.718 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.53.

Perpetual inventory control system has a mean response of 4.37 and a standard deviation of 0.704. The standard deviation of 0.704 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.37. Lastly, order cycling system has a mean response of 4.22 and a standard deviation of 0.866. The standard deviation of 0.866 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.22. In view of the results of the analysis, it can be deduced that economic order quantity had a more consistent response with a standard deviation of 0.718 and with a grand mean of 4.39. This implies that economic order quantity is the industry inventory practice and a control system that is being used to ensure profitability.

Table 3. Industry inventory practices and control systems to ensure cost savings

Cost Savings	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Two-bin System	4.06	0.887	Agree
Budgetary Control System	4.22	0.883	Agree
Economic Order Quantity	4.25	0.967	Agree
Perpetual Inventory Control System	4.04	0.898	Agree
Order Cycling System	3.91	0.965	Agree
Grand Mean	4.10		Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Undecided; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

The table above indicates that two-bin system has a mean response of 4.06 and the standard deviation is 0.887. The standard deviation of 0.887 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response. Budgetary control system has a mean response of 4.22 and a standard deviation of 0.883. The standard deviation of 1.396 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.22.

Economic order quantity has a mean response of 4.25 and a standard deviation of 0.967. The standard deviation of 0.967 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.25. Perpetual inventory control system has a mean response of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 0.898. The standard deviation of 0.898 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.04. Order cycling system has a mean response of 3.91 and a standard deviation of 0.965. The standard deviation of 0.965 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 3.91.

In view of the results of the analysis based on the respondent’s responses, it was seen that economic order quantity had a more consistent response with a standard deviation of 4.25 and with a grand mean of 4.10. This implies that the economic order quantity is the industry inventory practice and control systems that is being used to ensure cost savings.

Table 4. Industry inventory practices and control systems to ensure lead time

Lead Time	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Two-bin System	4.11	0.794	Agree
Budgetary Control System	4.00	0.933	Agree
Economic Order Quantity	4.15	1.020	Agree
Perpetual Inventory Control System	3.95	1.086	Agree
Order Cycling System	4.02	0.987	Agree
Grand Mean	4.05		Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Undecided; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

In the table above, the analysis indicates that two-bin system has a mean response of 4.11 and the standard deviation is 0.794. The standard deviation of 0.794 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response. In budgetary control system, it shows that it has a mean response of 4 and a standard deviation of 0.933. The standard deviation of 0.933 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.00.

Economic order quantity has a mean response of 4.15 and a standard deviation of 1.020. The standard deviation of 1.02 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.15. Perpetual inventory control system has a mean response of 3.95 and a standard deviation of 1.086. The standard deviation of 1.086 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 3.95. Order cycling system has a mean response of 4.02 and a standard deviation of 0.987. The standard deviation of 0.987 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.02. In view of the results of the analysis, economic order quantity had a more consistent response with a standard deviation of 1.02 with a grand mean of 4.05. This implies that economic order quantity is the industry inventory practice and control systems that is being used to ensure lead time.

Table 5. Industry inventory practices and control systems to ensure stock out

Stock Out	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Two-bin System	4.19	0.778	Agree
Budgetary Control System	4.26	0.747	Agree
Economic Order Quantity	4.28	0.986	Agree
Perpetual Inventory Control System	4.19	0.779	Agree
Order Cycling System	3.92	0.988	Agree
Grand Mean	4.17		Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49 – Disagree; 2.50-3.49 – Undecided; 3.50-4.49 – Agree; 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Agree

In the table above, the analysis of two-bin system shows a mean response of 4.19 and the standard deviation is 0.778. The standard deviation of 0.778 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response. The budgetary control system has a mean response of 4.26 and a standard deviation of 0.747. The standard deviation of 0.747 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.26.

Economic order quantity has a mean response of 4.28 and a standard deviation of 0.986. The standard deviation of 0.986 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.19. Perpetual inventory control system has a mean response of 4.19 and a standard deviation of 0.779. The standard deviation of 0.779 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 4.19. Lastly, order cycling system has a mean response of 3.922 and a standard deviation of 0.988. The standard deviation of 0.988 therefore indicates how far the responses deviate from the mean response of 3.92.

From the above result, economic order quantity had a more consistent response with a standard deviation of 0.986 and with a grand mean of 4.1684. This implies that economic order quantity is the industry inventory practice and control system that is being used to ensure stock out.

Table 6. Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.276	.076	.051	.96051

In order to test the hypothesis earlier formulated in this study, model specifications were drawn for the study and presented on the following tables:

Table 7. Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	f	Sig.
Regression	8.499	3	2.833	3.071	0.031
Residual	103.329	112	.923		
Total	111.828	115			

Table 8. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.458	.727		3.380	.001
PRFITAB/LDTM	.117	.125	.085	.935	.352
CSTSAV/STKOUT	.051	.095	.050	.540	.591
INVPRACNTRSYS	.250	.092	.250	2.702	.008

The model summary indicated an R2 value of 0.076. This means that about 7.6% of the variability in organization development is accounted for by all the selected aspects of organizational structure (PRFITAB/LDTM, CSTSAV/STKOUT and INVPRACNTRSYS). The ANOVA shows the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The coefficient table shows the level of the effect of the various aspects of organizational structure on employee interpersonal relationship. The following are decision based on the analysis in the coefficient table.

Ho: *There is no significant difference between profitability and lead time.*

The p-value obtained is lesser than 5% level of significance used for this study. The ANOVA table revealed that the relationship is significant ($p=0.031$). Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This therefore means that there is a significant difference between profitability and lead time.

Ho: *There is no significant difference between cost saving and stock-out.*

The ANOVA table reveals that there is a significant relationship ($p=0.031$). The p-value obtained is lesser than the significance level of 5% used for this study. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. We therefore conclude that there is a significant difference between cost saving and stock-out.

Ho: *Inventory practices and policies does not have any significant difference on the development of Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas company.*

The coefficient table reveals that there is a significant relationship ($p=0.031$). The p-value obtained is lesser than 0.05 level of significance used for this study. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This therefore means that economic order quantity does not have any significant difference In the development of Abumorako and Sons Oil and Gas.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Inventory control management and practices have been classified as one of the most important factors of every organizational development; with an efficient use of its control mechanism, such organization is sure to experience its development. Any organization's capacity to create an inventory control management system will be based on how much it believes it will benefit from the program.

The findings of this study make it relevant that, when implemented correctly, an efficient inventory control management system may benefit enterprises much. Some of the benefits associated with the use of the various inventory practices as postulated earlier in the study includes; profitability which is seen as the ability of any organization effectively utilize its resources to generate revenues in excess of its expenses. In the same vein, a cost saving of the organization portends a great relief for organization and thereby enabling them to reduce costs and maximize their profit base which is the core objective of the organization development.

In addition, lead time which is seen as the latency between the initiation and execution of a process like the efficient placement of an order and delivery of products (Drury & Tayles, 2020). And stock-out situation which can be handled if organization take a keen look at inventory practice to avoid running out of stock. Organizations must take a proactive approach to the problem since they can no longer downplay the significance of developing and maintaining an efficient inventory control management system. The organization should ensure that they practice effective and efficient use of inventory control mechanism and its inventory system to help enhance their profitability by constantly using its resources to generate revenues in excess for the organizational development. The organization should deliberately ensure that unnecessary cost are minimized to enable them to constantly increase their profit base by using EOQ and not only budgetary control system. Organizations should effectively and timely adopt lead time process between the initiation and execution of a process like the placement of an order and delivery of products.

The organization should consciously ensure that they do not run out of stock to avoid their inventory to be exhausted, which would lead to losing their customers. They should endeavor in the continuous training of its staff to enable them effectively to apply their skills in carrying out their assign duties. In the area of inventory the management needs to employ qualified workers who are specialized in inventory control and management and not using staff without adequate knowledge and skill just to save cost. Although EOQ was considered as the most important in the organization top inventory control system but from the findings budgetary system was also ticked to make it so close in the area where EOQ is well-known to be the solution.

The use of EOQ system is either not well understood or not properly used by the organization. Therefore, an organization needs to see the important of EOQ since it covers range of inventory management and its importance in the area of cost management. The organization should also employ the use of modern technology and inventory software to assist in the check of its inventory such as: barcode assistant, tools for reporting, forecasting inventory levels, inventory fluctuation alerts, accounting plug-in, and inventory synchronization capabilities.

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